

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series

Vol.XVI. Book. I-IV

January-December

2024

Sanskrit Research Foundation

T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

KIRANĀVALĪ

ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

Editor

Prof. Dr.M. Manimohan (Rtd)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.m.manimohan@gmail.com

Executive Editor

Prof. Dr.C.S.Sasikumar (Rtd.)

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.sasikumarcs@gmail.com

Managing Editor

Prof. Dr.G.Narayanan

Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady

dr.g.narayanan@gmail.com

Editorial board

Dr.V.Sisupalapanikkar, Professor of Sanskrit(Rtd.) Uty. of Kerala

Dr.K.Muthulakshmi, Professor of Vedanta, S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.R.Vijayakumar, Professor of Vyakarana(Rtd.), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.P.Chithambaran, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd),S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.P.K.Dharmarajan, Professor of Sahitya, (Rtd) S.S.U.S. Kalady

Dr.K.K.Sundaresan, Associate Professor in Vedanta, SSUS.Kalady

Dr.S.Sobhana, Professor of Vedanta (Rtd), S.S.U.S.Kalady

Dr.T.Devarajan, Professor of Sanskrit (Rtd), University of Kerala

Associate Editor

Dr.R.Jinu

Associate Professor, Dept of English,

Noorul Islam Centre For Higher Education, Kumaracoil,

Thuckalay, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu

jichelnu@gmail.com

Contents

Editors Note	5
Fractions or kalāsavarṇa - Concepts in the Gaṇitasārasaṅgraha (G.S.S) of Mahāvira	Dr. P.M.Mini 7
Vrikshayurveda Literature- A Review	Dr. K.Murali 12
Existence Of Mind and its Function: Śrī Śankara's Perspective	Dr. V Vasanthakumari 23
Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva	Dr. Yamuna.K 30
Parāstotra - Edition and Study	Dr. J.P. Prajith 37
Alienation through Exile: A Critical Introspection into John Dos Passos' Nineteen Nineteen	Dr. Sanil T. Sunny 44
The Evolution of Indian Sculptural Art: Interaction with Western Styles and Development of Modernism	Dr. T.G Jyothilal 49
Scope of Sanskrit Studies in the Kerala Context	Dr.Shylaja S 55
Desamangalam Srikantha Variar - A Versatile Scholar	Dr.V.P.Udayakumar 67
A Comprehensive Review of Adharaneeya and Dharaneeya Vega	Dr. H.A.Anu, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Haroon Irshad, Dr. Leena P.Nair 72
A Significant Emphasis on Charakokta Chaturvidha Pariksha	Dr.Kesavan.V G, Dr.Haroon Irshad, Dr.Leena P.Nair, Dr. Haritha Chandran 84
Concept Of Manas- A Glimpse from Yoga Darsana	Dr. Anu Gopal, Dr. Haritha Chandran, Dr. Leena P Nair, Dr. Haroon Irshad 96
Women Life in Royal Harem- A Study Based on Nāṭyaśāstra And Mālavikāgnimitra	Dr. Ajitha T S 106
Effective Strategies For Implementing The Integrated Teacher Education Programme Under NEP- 2020	Prof. K.K. Harshkumar, Dr. Anand Rautmale 113
“Pancha Mahabhuta in Ayurveda: Understanding and Practical Applications”	Dr. Aswiny Sreekumar.T 121
“Dynamic Portrayals of Women in Amarushatak: Unravelling Love, Creation, Destruction, Submission, and Dominance”	Dr. Preeti R. Pujara 135
Literary Representation of the Ashtamudi Lake sketched through Poetic Imagery: An Exploration based on Selected Poems in Malayalam	Jayalekshmi J 145
Reviving Classical Narratives: Exploring the Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Significance of Sanskrit Literature in Contemporary Contexts	Dr. Yeshpal, 155
Vedic Thought on Nakshatra Science	Dr. Kanta 172
Vedāntic Reflections in Kālidāsa's Literature: A Journey through Ancient Wisdom	Dr. K. K. Abdul Majeed 179
The Transformative Power of Yogic Meditation: Insights from the Isha Upanishad	Dev Prakash Gujela, Neha Gujela 188
Sanskrit: The Language of Innovation in Ancient Indian Knowledge Systems.	Dr. Abdul Rasheed K. 197
The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion	Dr. Abdulla Sha R., Dr. Midhun P., 207

Concept of Guṇa in Bhagavad Gīta	Dr. Shyji K.K.	212
Pancatantram's perspective of accepting an 'hors de combat'	Kasthuri P. K.	217
Integral Yoga of Sri Aurobindo	Remya.S	223
The Historical Aspects Of 'Translation' (Anuvādam) - An Overview	Dr. Sajeesh C S	227
The Malayali Diaspora in the US: A close reading of Mira Jacob	Nirupama Suneetha	235
From Elancon To Kollam: The Transformation of A Port City	Gowri S Panicker	242
Influence of Nārayanīya on Kṛṣṇagīti	Dr Jayanisha K	255
Subverting Ableist Binaries: An Analysis of the Confluence of Disability Studies and Blue Humanities in Toni Crowther's From Wheelchair to Water	Sneha Jacob	263
Connecting the Concept of 'Avatar' to the Concept of Consciousness in Upanishads	Venugopalan P.M	269
Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature	Soorya A.P	281
चिन्सुखेन प्रतिपादितं अविद्यालक्षणम्	डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्	285
सामाजिकसमस्यापरिहारे भरतीयज्ञानपरम्परान्तर्गतस्य योगशास्त्रस्य स्थानम्	डा. श्रीजित् टि.जि	289
पतञ्जलिकालीनः लोकव्यवहारः-महाभाष्याधारेण एकमनुशीलनम्	डा.रूपा. वि	293
मानवीयमूल्यबोधोत्तरणे मूच्छकटिकम्	ड.मृत्युञ्जयमण्डलः परेशकैवर्त्यः	299
रघुवंशमहाकाव्ये रसतत्त्वसमीक्षणम्	काञ्चनवारिकः	304
नारीचैतन्योद्बोधे शङ्खनादः	डॉ टुम्पा जाना	308
आधुनिकसंस्कृतसाहित्ये गलज्जलिकायाः वैशिष्ट्यम्	सतीश चन्द्र दास	313
श्रीमच्छंकराचार्यकृतच्छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यस्य कतिपयशब्दवाक्यानां रूपवाक्यशब्दार्थतत्त्वनिरूपणम्	रणिता घोष	321
सदाचारो वेदाश्च ।	डा.अशोक कुमार एन्.के.	327
साम्प्रतिकसन्दर्भे अपरिग्रहः	डॉ. शुभमयपाहाडी	331
मनुसंहिता : 'ब्रह्मतत्त्व' विषयकम् एकं संक्षिप्तं मतम्	अमल कुमार कर	335
श्रीकाशीमठाधीशानां श्रीमत्सुधीन्द्रतीर्थानां स्तोत्रेषु छन्दांसि तथा सौन्दर्यम्	दिव्यश्री जगदीश पै बि. , & भास्कर वि भट्टः	339
सिद्धान्तग्रन्थेषु ब्राह्मणमानम्	डा. राघवेंद्रः	347
एतत्संज्ञेत्यत्र कः समासः	डा. गोपालकृष्णन् रघुः	352
मेघदूतस्य सांस्कृतिकमीमांसा	डा. सत्येन्दु शर्मा	356
जान्-म्यूर-प्रणीतस्य 'श्रीपौलचरित्रम्' इति महाकाव्यस्य संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रदृष्ट्या समीक्षामिका विमृष्टिः	डा. सौम्यजित् सेनः	360
आधुनिकयुगे संस्कृतशिक्षा प्रसारार्थं विद्यासागरस्यावदानम्	डः तानिया-सिकदारः	369
तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।	आतिरा. जि	372
अद्वैतसिद्धेः मङ्गलश्लोकस्य अप्रामाण्यशङ्कावारणम्	कार्तिक शर्मा के , ड. हरिकृष्ण शर्मा के.एन्	376
न्यायव्याकरणतन्त्रानुरोधे पदस्वरूपविवेचनम्	प्रणबेष् भट्टाचार्यः	381
पीयूषवर्षश्रीजयदेवाचार्य-श्रीकेशवमिश्रयोः मते शान्तरसविमर्शः	सत्येनशीटः	387
आलंकारिकदण्डिस्वीकृतः शब्दालङ्कारप्रपञ्चः	डॉ. शुभ्रजित् सेनः	393
लिधा एव पदशब्दस्य प्रवृत्तिः	डा. सुदीप-मण्डलः	400
About the journal		407

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14684638>

Extraction of historicity from Sanskrit literature

Soorya A.P¹

Introduction

Sanskrit is a language that is rich in its literary merit and depth. Whenever a question arises against the studies in classical languages like Sanskrit, Greek and Latin the cursor points to the richness in literature and cultural studies fostered by them. According to Sriman Narayana Murthy “The studies in the classical language is like Sanskrit, Greek, and Latin are neither an entertaining recreation nor a leisure time curiosity. It offers an opportunity for a unique intellectual experience of high educational value.” He also quotes that “The present becomes meaningful when it is beer upon the past. Thus, to link closely with the past and explore the past with only the present in mind becomes most purposive research. Cultural change is the aim of every nation for the benefit of its people” (Murti 2-3).

Sanskrit literature possess literal as well as historical factors. Some of the literature indicates directly to the historical facts, glorification, and unauthentic findings. The historicity in Sanskrit literature can be found mainly in two types, direct availability from works and indirect or unconscious manifestation. This paper focuses on the relevance of cultural studies as well as the processing of historical facts from it. The first portion of this paper discusses about the relevance of cultural studies. Some authors convey their personal details and historical details in their work. The visible historicity in such literature is the second topic of discussion. The third is the process of filtration of hidden historical facts from the

1. Research scholar, Department of Sanskrit Vyakarana, Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalad, Email : achusoorya1@gmail.com,

Sanskrit literature.

Relevance of cultural studies

The terms like behaviour, conceptual and physical human constructions come under the realm of culture. It is dynamic in nature. In a literary work, there will be several historical and cultural factors. One can study about any cultural factor. All of these comes under cultural studies. But they did not consider in the periodical discussions. In 1950s a group of thinkers from Newleft of America, strongly reacted against the orthodox Marxism and liberal humanism. Cultural studies which are consider seriously nowadays are the contribution of the reaction made by the Newleft group. They were revisionists. They claimed that they were Marxist till the end. Therefore, cultural studies can be considered as another branch of Marxism (Dr.D. Benjamin)

India is a country enriched by its cultural features. Hence there is a necessity to unravel the history through culture. History of a place can be extracted from the mentality of people, archaeological and epigraphical evidences and customs and traditions. Language is the direct reflection of mentality of its speakers. Therefore, literature in those periods become relevant. Even though the archaeological evidences fail to find the history, cultural studies are the only dependable source of knowledge. For example, we have no clear inscriptional evidence dating back to third century B.C. The archaeological survivals in the Harappa and Mohenjodaro excavations still pose serious problems regarding their origin and hopefully cultural studies might define them (Murti 4).

Direct access to historicity

Sanskrit is a language that has existed in India since ancient times. The first poetry was Rigveda. After which there was a continuous flow of literature in Sanskrit. Several texts from the ancient times remain undefined. Even if the name of author is known, no other details are available about the identity of the poet and the period in which it was written. In contrast to such texts some authors mention their details in their works or attach references to other texts.

Melputtūr Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭathiri, the author of *Nārāyaṇīya* gave away his personal details in his grammar text named *Prakriyāsarvaswa*. There are many anecdotes about him which are

mostly fanciful with little foundation and may not be reliable for research purpose. *Melputtūr* is the name of his family. His father was *Mātr̥datta* and house was situated on the banks of the river, now known as *Bhāratapuzha*, which joins the sea at *Ponnāni* on the west coast. All the above-mentioned details are contained in:

भूखण्डे केरलराज्ये सरिदमिह निलामुत्तरेणैव नवा-
क्षेत्राद्भव्यूतिमाले पुनरुपरिनवग्रामनाम्नि स्वधाम्नि ।
धर्मिष्ठाद्भट्टतन्त्राद्यखिलमतपटोर्मातृदत्तद्विजेन्द्रा-
ज्जातो नारायणाख्यो निरवहदतुलां देवनारायणज्ञाम् ॥ (Bhaṭṭathiri 119)

In Kerala, only a *gavyūdi* to the north of the river *Nilā*, in the place called *Nāvā* (modern *Tirunnāvāya*), in the house named *uparīnāvā-grāma* (*Melputtūr* in Malayalam), born of the great Dharmīṣṭha, *Mātr̥datta*, well versed in all branches of learning systems of Bhaṭṭa, and very pious, author named *Narayana*, have fully carried out the orders of *Dēvanārāyaṇa*.

Similarly, *Nagēśabhaṭṭa* marked his details in his text. *Nagēśabhaṭṭa* is a grammarian, author of several grammatical texts such as *Śabdendhuśekhara*, *Manjūṣa* and *Paribhāṣendhuśekhara*. In his text *Śabdendhuśekhara*, he mentioned the details like names of his father, mother, and the ruler of that time.

पातञ्जले महाभाष्ये कृतभूरिपरिश्रमः ।
शिवभट्टसुतो धीमान् सतीदेव्यास्तु गर्भजः ॥
याचकानां कल्पतरोररिकक्षहताशनात् ।
शृङ्गवेरपुराधीशाद् रामतो लब्धजीविकः ॥ (Bhaṭṭa 1-2)

These are the first two verses of *Mangalaśloka* in *Śabdendhuśekhara* text. Here he describes himself as the commentator of *Mahābhāṣya* out which arises that this text has written only after the completion of *Mahābhāṣya* commentary named *Udyota*. Then says that he is the son of *Śivabhaṭṭa* and *Satidēvi*. He resided in *Sṛṅgaverapura*, which was under the rule of *Rāmasimha*. These details are available directly from the slokas.

Samgrah, the text was written by *Vyadiḥ* which had not been discovered yet. The evidence of this text is depicted in *Mahābhāṣya* and *Vākyapadīya*.

Extraction of historicity from non-explicit information

Extraction of historicity in Sanskrit literature is relatively a tough task. Even though it is not easy, through proper analysis of content we

can access them. Historical kavya is one of the categories of literature. *Mūṣakavaṃṣa* of *Atula* is a well-known historical literature that describes the history of *Mūṣaka Kula*. Each piece of literature has its own historical and political sides. The history in those texts may be hidden within the work itself. Most of the historical kavyas in Kerala are based on the life of rulers. Glorification of events and praise of kingship were common among them. Extraction of substantial events from them remains a herculean task. For that, the researcher must be aware of the history of that period thoroughly.

The earliest Indian poetry that has come down to us is found in Rigveda. It is well known that this work consists of sacred songs and that its interest to a modern student is historical, not poetical. But at the same time, it would be incorrect to think that the work is devoid of aesthetic merit (Thapar). Sanskrit literature possess such historical events and literal merits. Although not directly connected with the history of Sanskrit literature, the subject of the history of the settlement of the indo-Aryans in the Rigveda is interesting.

Conclusions

There has been continuous flow of literature in Sanskrit from the Vedic period and it can stand as an epitome of cultural studies. Sanskrit literature can be used as a tool to study culture and understand history deeply. The historic approach in Sanskrit literature can be applied in two ways according to the direct availability of information and by the hidden or indirect manifestation of history. When several available Sanskrit texts provide the necessary direct information, indirect historical information can be extracted through proper analysis of text.

Works cited

- Hiriyanna M., Sanskrit studies, Kavyalaya publishers, Mysore, 2002
 Murti, Srimannarayana M., Methodology in Indological research, Bharatiya Book corporation, Delhi, 2018.
 Bhaṭṭathiri, Melputtūr Nārāyaṇa, Prakriyāsarvaswa, edited by C Kunhan Raja, University of madras, 1941
 Bhaṭṭa, Nageśa, Brhat-sabdendhusekhara, Edited by Sri Sitarama Sastri, Varanasi, 1996
 Thapar, Romila. Sakuntala: Texts, Readings, Histories, Kali for women publishers, New Delhi, 1999

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,